

CYCLIZATION REACTIONS WITH REAGENTS CONTAINING A CAGE SUBSTITUTE

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By a cyclocondensation reaction known as the Biginelli reaction, tetrahydropyrimidines and thiotetrahydropyrimidines containing an adamantyl substituent at positions 1 and 4 of the heterocycle were synthesized. The yields of target products ranged from 46 to 76% depending on the type of substituents (X=O or X=S, R=Ad- or AdCH₂-). Intramolecular condensation of N-adamantoylglycine yielded 2-(1-adamantyl)-5(4H)-oxazolone in 61% yield.

Keywords: Biginelli reaction, 6-Methyl-4-phenyl-5-ethoxycarbonyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one, adamantyl-containing ureas, thioureas, aldehydes, N-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine, 2-(1-adamantyl)-4-benzylidene-5-oxazolone, 2-(1-adamantyl)-5(4H)-oxazolone, dicyclohexylcarbodiimide.

Materials and methods

Chromatograms and LC/MS spectra were obtained on an "Agilent 1100 Series" instrument equipped with an "Agilent LC/MSD SL" detector.

¹H NMR spectra (400 MHz and 500 MHz) were recorded on Varian Mercury-400 and Bruker Avance DRX 500 NMR spectrometers with TMS as an internal standard.

The IR spectra of samples in KBr pellets containing 0.25% of the substance were recorded on a Specord 75IR instrument.

All reagents were obtained from commercially available sources (Aldrich, Fluka) and were used without further purification.

Results and discussion.*Biginelli reaction with reagents containing a cage substitute*

In the interaction of benzaldehyde, urea and acetoacetic ester in a molar ratio of 1:2:1 in the presence of a catalytic amount of hydrochloric acid, as shown by Biginelli, 6-methyl-4-phenyl-5-ethoxycarbonyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-2-one [1]. Later it turned out that not only aromatic, but also aliphatic aldehydes enter into this condensation [1–4]. At the same time, in addition to urea and thiourea, it was possible to use their N-substituted derivatives [5]. Thus, the Biginelli reaction turned out to be one of the important methods for

the synthesis of various tetrahydropyrimidine derivatives. An important role in the formation of the latter is played by intermediate amidoalkylating agents of the or type, which can be obtained as a result of the condensation of urea with aldehydes or acetoacetic ester [6]. Instead of aldehydes and acetoacetic ester, it was possible to use the products of their condensation obtained previously [3].

In recent years, interest in the Biginelli reaction has increased significantly, due to the search for drugs that affect the cardiovascular system among tetrahydropyrimidine derivatives. In a number of these compounds, pharmaceutical agents have indeed been found, having a pronounced hypotensive effect and a negative inotropic effect [7, 8].

On the other hand, the presence of an adamantyl substituent in compounds containing pharmacophore groups is known to enhance or impart new properties to potential physiologically active substrates.

The aim of this part is to obtain tetrahydropyrimidines containing adamantyl radical in different positions of the ring.

The starting adamantyl-containing ureas, thioureas, and aldehydes were obtained by standard procedures.

A few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added to a mixture of reagents in acetic acid (X = O) or ethanol (X = S) in the ratio indicated above and boiled for 8 (X = O) or 12 hours (X = S). The solvent

was removed in vacuo. The residue was crystallized from methanol.

Yields of tetrahydropyrimidines are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Yields of synthesized tetrahydropyrimidines (4), (7).

Compound	Yield, %			
	X = O		X = S	
	Ad-	AdCH ₂ -	Ad-	AdCH ₂ -
4	51	73	46	68
7	47	72	52	76

As can be seen from the table, the yields of compounds containing adamantyl radical are lower than those of compounds with adamantylmethyl radical. This can be explained by spatial difficulties arising in the first case.

Cyclization of *n*-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine

The only known example of an oxazolone containing an adamantyl radical in position 2 is 2-(1-adamantyl)-4-benzylidene-5-oxazolone, obtained by the condensation of *N*-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine (1) with benzaldehyde under Erlenmeyer reaction conditions [9].

Continuing research in the field of chemistry of α -amino acids of the adamantane series [10–13], we synthesized for the first time stable 2-(1-adamantyl)-

5(4H)-oxazolone (2) from acylated glycine (1), an adamantyl analogue of hippuric acid. Compound (2) is formed by refluxing *N*-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine (1) in anhydrous chloroform for 4 hours in the presence of dicyclohexylcarbodiimide in a yield of 61%.

The presence of a characteristic band at 1830 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum of compound (2) unambiguously indicates its cyclic structure [14]. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of a solution of this compound in deuterioacetone in the region of 4.25 ppm, there is a singlet of protons of the methylene group at position 4 of oxazolone (2). The addition of trifluoroacetic acid to the analyzed solution leads to the opening of the azlactone ring and the formation of mixed anhydride (3), as evidenced by the appearance of a doublet with a spin-spin coupling constant of 6 Hz at δ 3.9 ppm.

An attempt to carry out the cyclization of acylamino acid (1) by the action of trifluoroacetic anhydride led to the formation of mixed anhydride (3) of N-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine and trifluoroacetic acid. The isolated compound (3) spontaneously slowly cyclizes with elimination of a trifluoroacetic acid molecule, which is confirmed by the presence in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the corresponding signals of oxazolone (2) and anhydride (3) protons.

2-(1-Adamantyl)-5(4H)-oxazolone (2). To a solution of 0.92 g (4.4 mmol) of dicyclohexylcarbodiimide in 30 ml of anhydrous chloroform was added 1 g (4 mmol) of N-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine (1) and the mixture was boiled for 4 hours. After cooling, the precipitate of dicyclohexylurea was filtered off. The solvent was removed in vacuo. 20 ml of anhydrous pentane was added to the residue, and the mixture was boiled for 5 minutes. 0.38 g of compound (1) was isolated by filtration of the hot solution, m.p. 195 °C. The filtrate was cooled to 0 °C. The precipitate of oxazolone (2) was filtered off and recrystallized from pentane. Yield 0.56 g (61%), mp 59–60 °C. IR spectrum, ν , cm⁻¹: 1660 (C=N), 1830 (C=O). ¹H NMR spectrum, δ , ppm, (CD₃)₂CO : 1.3–2.15 m (15H), 4.25 s (CH₂).

Interaction of N-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine (1) with trifluoroacetic anhydride. To 0.2 g (0.85 mmol) N-(1-adamantylcarbonyl)glycine (1) with ice cooling and stirring 0.4 ml (2.55 mmol) of trifluoroacetic anhydride was added. The precipitate that formed was immediately filtered off under argon and washed with a small amount of cold anhydrous pentane. Yield of mixed anhydride (3) 0.26 g (92%), m.p. 77–78 °C. ¹H NMR spectrum, δ , ppm : 1.3–2.15 m (15H), 3.9 d [CH₂, compound (3), J 6 Hz], 4.25 s [CH₂, compound (2)], 7.37 m [NH, compound (3)].

Conclusions

1) A method for the synthesis of adamantyl-containing tetrahydropyrimidines was developed for the first time. Testing them for physiological activity is recommended.

2) The possibility and method of cyclization of N-adamantoylglycine into 2-(1-Adamantyl)-5(4H)-oxazolone is shown. The possibility of converting its fluorine-containing amino acid derivative is shown.

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